

THE BENEFITS OF LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE.

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Annotation: English language is considered one of the global languages around the world, and learning this language benefits both learners and the society. We can count variety of benefits of learning English as a second language. So, in this article the author tends to feature some of the most significant keys of learning English as a second language.

Annotatsiya: Ingliz tili butun dunyo bo'ylab global tillardan biri hisoblanadi va bu tilni o'rganish o'quvchilarga ham, jamiyatga ham foyda keltiradi. Ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganishning turli afzalliklarini sanashimiz mumkin. Shunday qilib, ushbu maqolada muallif ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganishning eng muhim kalitlarini ko'rsatishga intiladi.

Аннотация: Английский язык считается одним из глобальных языков во всем мире, и изучение этого языка приносит пользу как учащимся, так и обществу. Мы можем перечислить множество преимуществ изучения английского как второго языка. Итак, в этой статье автор стремится описать некоторые из наиболее важных ключей к изучению английского как второго языка.

Key words: English, second language, learning, learners, benefits.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tili, ikkinchi til, o'rganish, o'rganuvchilar, foyda.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, второй язык, обучение, учащиеся, льготы

English as a world language is not merely an international language. The notion of international language can be understood as a language which is used in any international communication which involves people from two or more countries. Japanese is an international language, but it is not a global language. Japanese is often used by people who communicate with Japanese people, usually in the area in which Japanese people, tradition, political power and/ or business are dominant. Learning English as a second language offers a wide range of benefits, both personally and professionally. Here are some key advantages

Global Communication: English is the most widely spoken language in the world, making it a crucial tool for communication in various international settings, such as business, travel, and academia. As an active traveler I can say

that I had no difficulties while traveling abroad. There are more than 7,000 official languages around the world and we do not have the ability to learn all of them, so what is the solution? To learn a language which is used globally and one of them is English.

Career Opportunities: Proficiency in English can open up a plethora of career opportunities, as many multinational companies require employees to have strong English language skills. Being able to use the language as a second language you can make process at work. Among the candidates who wanted to apply for the job the ones who speak more foreign languages get the job.

Education: English is often the language of instruction in universities and academic institutions worldwide. Learning English can enhance your educational prospects and enable you to access a broader range of resources and information. Authoritative universities, colleges all around the world offer lessons, courses in English. And the main sources of information written in English too.

Cultural Exchange: English is the language of many influential works of literature, music, and film. By learning English, you can engage with and appreciate diverse cultures and perspectives.

Personal Growth: Learning a new language challenges your cognitive abilities and enhances your problem-solving skills, memory retention, and multitasking abilities. It can also boost your self-confidence and improve your overall mental agility.

Networking: English proficiency allows you to connect with people from different backgrounds and cultures, expanding your social and professional networks. English proficiency can be a valuable asset when it comes to networking with individuals from diverse backgrounds and cultures.

Being able to communicate effectively in English can help you build relationships, collaborate on projects, and exchange ideas with people from around the world. This can lead to new opportunities, cross-cultural understanding, and a broader perspective on various issues.

Additionally, networking in English can enhance your professional reputation and credibility, as it demonstrates your willingness to engage with a global audience and adapt to different communication styles.

Overall, English proficiency can facilitate meaningful connections and open doors to a wide range of possibilities in both your personal and professional life.

English is widely spoken in tourist destinations around the world. Knowing English can make your travel experiences smoother and more enjoyable.

Access to Information: The majority of online content is available in English. By mastering the language, you can access a wealth of information, resources, and opportunities on the internet. Overall, learning English as a second language can

significantly enrich your life, broaden your horizons, and provide you with a competitive edge in the globalized world.

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